

A logical difficulty with the concept of probability as uncertainty

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Abstract

This paper describes a logical inconsistency that arises when expressing uncertainty about a constant θ using a continuous probability distribution. When the distribution is updated by correct combination with a distribution obtained from new information, the result is not invariant to an arbitrary non-linear transformation from θ to $h(\theta)$. The conclusion to be drawn is that the theory of probability is not always capable of describing epistemic uncertainty.

This is a pre-print of a manuscript shortly to be submitted to an unspecified statistics journal. The manuscript extends a result published in *Measurement: Sensors* 24:100416 (2022) to apply to subjective probability.

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This paper describes a logical inconsistency that arises when expressing uncertainty about a constant θ using a continuous probability distribution. When the distribution is updated by correct combination with a distribution obtained from new information, the result is not invariant to an arbitrary non-linear transformation from θ to $h(\theta)$. The conclusion to be drawn is that the theory of probability is not always capable of describing epistemic uncertainty.

1 Introduction

Probability is an abstract mathematical construct obeying axioms, and the theory of probability is built on these axioms in an agreed way. But the legitimate roles of probability in the expression of uncertainty have long been contentious. For many readers, the subject of any legitimate statement of probability must be the potential outcome in a hypothetically repeatable procedure, as in a frequentist analysis. In that context, uncertainty is aleatory, i.e., it relates to unpredictability. But for many other readers, a legitimate statement of probability can also be made about any unknown constant, as in Bayesian statistics or fiducial inference. And in that context, uncertainty is epistemic, i.e., it relates to doubt (about something that has already happened). In this paper, we examine the second point of view, under which the unknown value of a constant might be described by a probability distribution. Our analysis applies only to constants that exist on continuous scales, so it involves the following premise, P:

P: it is meaningful and legitimate to express uncertainty about a constant θ that exists on a continuous scale by attributing θ a probability distribution.

In what follows we conclude that P is false, giving a proof by contradiction. This conclusion has far-reaching implications for the fields of Bayesian inference and fiducial inference, which both rely on the truth of P. The argument given here is brief and straightforward, and if the conclusion is to be dismissed then something in this argument must be shown to be incorrect.

Section 2 derives the unique pdf to be obtained under P when melding pdfs obtained two from disjoint sets of information or beliefs about the same constant. Subsequently, Section 3 shows that

the result obtained in Section 2 leads to a logical contradiction, which implies that P must be false. Section 4 contains discussion.

2 Combining probability distributions for the same quantity

Imagine that unknown constant quantities θ_1 and θ_2 exist on a continuous scale. Suppose I accept premise P and attribute the probability density functions $f_1(x)$ and $f_2(x)$ to θ_1 and θ_2 based on separate, i.e., disjoint, sets of information or beliefs. Let θ'_1 and θ'_2 be the values of θ_1 and θ_2 when rounded onto a scale with origin zero and unit of discretization δ . Then the probability mass functions of θ'_1 and θ'_2 are

$$p_i(x) = \int_{x-\delta/2}^{x+\delta/2} f_i(z) dz \quad x = \dots, -\delta, 0, \delta, \dots \quad i = 1, 2.$$

Because the two sets of information or beliefs are disjoint, the joint probability mass function I attribute to θ'_1 and θ'_2 is

$$p(x_1, x_2) = p_1(x_1)p_2(x_2) \quad x_1, x_2 = \dots, -\delta, 0, \delta, \dots$$

Suppose I now learn that θ_1 and θ_2 are equal, in which case θ'_1 and θ'_2 must be equal. Then, by the rule of conditional probability $\Pr(A|B) = \Pr(A \cap B) / \Pr(B)$, the updated joint mass function must obey

$$p(x_1, x_2 | \theta'_1 = \theta'_2) = 0 \quad x_1 \neq x_2$$

and

$$p(x, x | \theta'_1 = \theta'_2) = \frac{p_1(x)p_2(x)}{\sum_{z=-\infty}^{\infty} p_1(z)p_2(z)}.$$

It follows that the probability mass function that I then attribute to the single quantity $\theta' \equiv \theta'_1 = \theta'_2$ is also given by

$$p(x) = \frac{p_1(x)p_2(x)}{\sum_{z=-\infty}^{\infty} p_1(z)p_2(z)}.$$

Dividing through by δ gives

$$\frac{p(x)}{\delta} = \frac{p_1(x)/\delta \times p_2(x)/\delta}{\sum_{z=-\infty}^{\infty} p_1(z)/\delta \times p_2(z)/\delta \times \delta},$$

and taking δ to zero shows that the corresponding probability density function (pdf) of the quantity $\theta \equiv \theta_1 = \theta_2$ is

$$f(x) = \frac{f_1(x)f_2(x)}{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f_1(z)f_2(z)dz}. \quad (1)$$

The point in time at which I discover that θ_1 and θ_2 are equal makes no difference to my final set of information or beliefs. So, this equation must also describe the probability density function obtained when combining two independently formed pdfs for a single quantity.

2.1 Example 1

Consider a fictitious example relating to uncertainty in measurement, which is a field of interest to the author, e.g., [1], and for which some international guidelines promote the attribution of pdfs to constants e.g., [2, Introduction], [3, 3.17]. Suppose a laboratory is given the task of measuring the resistance θ of a resistor with nominal value 1000Ω . The laboratory carries out its procedure and obtains the measured value 999.32Ω . A statement of measurement uncertainty must be provided with this. After taking into account all available information about the estimand θ and all local knowledge about the measurement procedure, the laboratory attributes θ the normal distribution with mean 999.32Ω and standard deviation 0.46Ω . Therefore, $f_1(x)$ is the pdf of this distribution.

Subsequently, the laboratory learns that the resistor was manufactured by a company with a stable manufacturing process that follows a frequency distribution with pdf $g(x)$, say the pdf of a uniform distribution with limits 999.1Ω and 1000.9Ω , (the hard limits perhaps being enforced in a step of quality control by rejection). Recognising that this is new information to be accommodated, the laboratory forms the pdf $f_2(x)$ by choosing $f_2(x) = g(x)$: there is no other sensible choice. The set of information or beliefs used to form $f_1(x)$ and the piece of information used to form $f_2(x)$ are disjoint, so the laboratory must update its representation of θ from $f_1(x)$ to the pdf given by $f(x)$ in (1), which will be the pdf of a doubly truncated normal distribution.

2.2 Example 2

Suppose that $f_i(x)$ is the pdf of a normal variable with mean μ_i and variance σ_i^2 , i.e., suppose that

$$f_i(x) \propto \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{x - \mu_i}{\sigma_i}\right)^2\right) \quad i = 1, 2.$$

Then, from (1),

$$f(x) \propto \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{x - \mu}{\sigma}\right)^2\right) \quad \mu \equiv \frac{\sigma_1^2 \mu_2 + \sigma_2^2 \mu_1}{\sigma_1^2 + \sigma_2^2} \quad \sigma^2 \equiv \frac{\sigma_1^2 \sigma_2^2}{\sigma_1^2 + \sigma_2^2},$$

which describes the pdf of a normal variable with mean μ and variance σ^2 , c.f., Elster [4, Section 3].

3 A logical contradiction

Straightforward reasoning has shown that, when two *independently formed* pdfs for the same quantity are combined, the unique result is (1). This result is noteworthy in its own right because there has been considerable discussion on how to combine pdfs attributed to the same quantity, some of which is mentioned in Section 4.3. However, as now described, a corollary of this result is of much greater significance.

Let us write $f_{\theta,i}$ and f_θ for f_i and f to indicate that the subject of these pdfs is θ . Suppose there is a meaningful unknown constant $\lambda = h(\theta)$, where h is a monotonic non-linear function. (In Example 1

above, λ could be the conductance of the resistor, which would be $1/\theta$.) Then, from the well-known result for the transformation of continuous variables,

$$f_{\lambda,i}(y) = f_{\theta,i}(x) \left| \frac{dx}{dy} \right| \quad \text{and} \quad f_{\lambda}(y) = f_{\theta}(x) \left| \frac{dx}{dy} \right| \quad y \equiv h(x).$$

If we apply the transformation after forming the combined pdf (1) then we obtain

$$f_{\lambda}(y) \propto f_{\theta,1}(x)f_{\theta,2}(x) \left| \frac{dx}{dy} \right|, \quad (2)$$

but if we apply the transformation to the component pdfs $f_{\theta,1}(x)$ and $f_{\theta,2}(x)$ before combining them then we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} f_{\lambda}(y) &\propto f_{\lambda,1}(y)f_{\lambda,2}(y) \\ &= f_{\theta,1}(x)f_{\theta,2}(x) \left| \frac{dx}{dy} \right|^2, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

in which the Jacobian $|dx/dy|$ is raised to the power of two. The function $h(\cdot)$ is non-linear, so the right-hand sides of (2) and (3) describe different pdfs. Thus, combining before transforming and transforming before combining, both of which are permitted by logical reasoning, lead to conflicting results for the pdf of λ . Moreover, if we apply the inverse transformation to (3) in order to recover the (combined) pdf of θ then we obtain

$$f_{\theta}(x) \propto f_{\theta,1}(x)f_{\theta,2}(x) \left| \frac{dx}{dy} \right|, \quad (4)$$

which differs from (1) — even if $h(\cdot)$ is an arbitrary non-linear function.

Clearly, something is amiss. The deductive steps in the argument are correct, and yet we have obtained a contradiction. Therefore, the fault must lie with the premise P. We conclude that, as a universal idea, P is false.

4 Discussion

4.1 The extent of the difficulty

After correct deductive argument from the premise P, we have reached a contradiction. Therefore, P must be false. Given the popularity of P, this conclusion is startling. However, the conclusion is to be accepted unless an error can be found either in the thought experiment of Section 2 or in the simple analysis of Section 3. As noted, our argument only applies to uncertainty about constants on a continuous scale. The argument does not hold when the quantity of interest lies on a discrete scale, because formula (1) for the transformation of variables is no longer relevant. So, there remains the possibility that a constant on a discrete scale can legitimately be attributed a probability *mass* function.

4.2 Objective and subjective understandings

The text of this paper uses the phrase “set of information or beliefs” a number of times. This expression has been employed to indicate that the conclusion holds whether the pdfs are regarded as objective entities expressing information or knowledge or as subjective entities expressing personal belief. In the field of metrology (measurement science), some international guidelines base the analysis of measurement uncertainty on the idea that assigning a pdf to an unknown quantity describes the “state of knowledge” of the metrologist, as if objectivity is being claimed, e.g., [2, Introduction?]. In that context, the contradiction described here has already been presented [5]–[8]. However, as seen in Example 1, the difficulty extends to the idea of subjective probability. So, although it is sometimes difficult to discern the interpretation that is given to a pdf for a constant, the validity of our conclusion is not affected: the contradiction applies however $f_1(x)$ and $f_2(x)$ are interpreted.

4.3 On the combination of pdfs for a constant

The step of updating a pdf in response to the receipt of new information is mandatory in Bayesian statistics, where the new information is usually a dataset from a sampling experiment and the analysis usually takes place according to Bayes’ theorem. But, in our context, the new information is a second pdf, and a different means of updating the first pdf must be found. The thought experiment described in Section 2 shows that the result when updating $f_1(x)$ to account for the existence of an independently formed pdf, $f_2(x)$, must be (1).

As described in review articles [9]–[11], various solutions have been proposed in the general task of combining pdfs for the same constant. One suggestion similar to (1) is the equation

$$f(x) = \frac{f_1(x)^{a_1} f_2(x)^{a_2}}{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f_1(z)^{a_1} f_2(z)^{a_2} dz}, \quad (5)$$

which describes a ‘logarithmic opinion pool’ of two pdfs with unspecified exponents a_1 and a_2 . This reduces to (1) when $a_1 = 1$ and $a_2 = 1$. It might be thought that substituting (5) for (1) and choosing $a_1 + a_2 = 1$ could avoid the contradiction. But that suggestion is faulty on at least two counts. First, the argument in Section 2 shows that the only logical solution is (1), which has $a_1 = 1$ and $a_2 = 1$: reason does not permit the analyst to use any other equation. Second, setting $a_1 + a_2 = 1$ violates the requirement that the addition of sets of information be associative: if we were to combine two pdfs before taking into account a third pdf then the result would depend on the way in which the sets of information were grouped. This objection is made clearer by considering how someone might logically weight the component pdfs. Each pdf is derived from a reliable set of information or beliefs, so each must be given equal weight. (The relative importance of each set of information would instead be fully represented by the ratio of the variances of the two component distributions.) So if we were going to choose a_1 and a_2 to sum to unity then the only defensible choice would be $a_1 = a_2 = 1/2$. Suppose we then combined two distributions according to (5) and subsequently received a third pdf, $f_3(x)$. Applying (5) with $f(x)$ and $f_3(x)$ would, in effect, weight the new pdf $f_3(x)$ twice as much as each of $f_1(x)$ and $f_2(x)$. But the overall combined set of information or beliefs does not depend on the order in which the three sets are received, so this would be unacceptable.

4.4 The device of using probability mass functions

It might seem that the derivation of (1) could be given using the pdfs for θ_1 and θ_2 without involving the mass functions for the discretized variables θ'_1 and θ'_2 . However, if we were to work with the bivariate pdf $f_1(u)f_2(v)$ instead of the bivariate probability mass function $p_1(x_1)p_2(x_2)$ then we would be conditioning on an event ' $\theta_1 = \theta_2$ ' that was attributed a probability of zero, which would render the proof incomplete because of Borel's paradox. (This was noted by Grientschnig and Lira [12], who were responding to an earlier derivation of (1) [13].) Choosing to apply the condition ' $\theta'_1 = \theta'_2$ ' to the bivariate probability *mass* function means that the event on which we are conditioning always has non-zero probability, in which case Borel's paradox has no relevance. (The step of proceeding to a continuous distribution by taking δ to zero occurs after the step in which the paradox would have applied.) So, the introduction of the discretized quantities θ'_1 and θ'_2 is merely a device to avoid the potential applicability of Borel's paradox.

5 Conclusion

If probability distributions are to be attributed to constants to correctly express uncertainty about them then the subsequent manipulation of these distributions must be carried out in a logical manner. A straightforward thought experiment shows that (1) describes the unique pdf that results from the combination of pdfs $f_1(x)$ and $f_2(x)$ used to represent disjoint sets of information or belief about a constant. But this result leads to a contradiction — a lack of invariance to a non-linear transformation of variables. The only explanation is that the premise of the analysis, P, is incorrect. Thus, it is not always meaningful to attribute a probability density function to an unknown constant: the theory of probability does not permit it.

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